

THE ROLE OF MINDMAPPING METHOD IN TEACHING VOCABULARY FOR STUDENTS OF LEVEL B 1

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Abstract : *The article discusses the importance of teaching vocabulary, particularly to B 1 level learner, and proposes the most productive ways to teach vocabulary using interactive as well as innovative techniques. There are also certain features of the memory and vocabulary acquisition process to consider. The aim of this study is to collect and introduce the best methods and strategies for teaching older learners vocabulary. This paper will be the right guide for EFL teachers who educate older learners including several types and instructions of strategies.*

Key words: Vocabulary acquisition strategies, adult learners, EFL teachers

There are a huge number of methods that can be applied within the framework of technology, however, due to the fact that it is not possible to describe all the existing methods and methods, we will focus on some of them, consider their purpose and we will indicate at which stage this or that method should be applied in the process of improving the lexical competence of foreign students in the language of philology, at the level of supply and super phrasal unity. And now we look through the information about different kinds of methods and strategies namely Mind mapping.

History shows that mind maps were used many centuries ago. They were used for learning and problem solving by many thinkers such as Leonardo Da Vinci, who used pictures, symbols and lines as a way to express his thoughts on paper. The pictures he used helped him explore his thoughts in many fields such as arts, horoscopes, machines, and biology. In the late sixteenth century and the earlier seventeenth, Galileo Galilee helped experts to revolutionize knowledge through his note-taking technique. Furthermore, Richard Feynman (a noble prize winner in physics) used to place all his theories of quantum and electrodynamics into visual and new diagrammatic forms. Tony Buzan, a British psychologist, invented mind maps

in the late 1960s as an alternative to standard note-taking methods. Buzan employed several components of mind mapping to enable people develop their own non-linear note taking. These components of mind mapping included the use of landscape paper, branches, symbols, colours, and core imagery. Mind maps were clearly utilised a long time ago. They were employed in a more straightforward manner than they are today. This demonstrates its significance as well as its simplicity and adaptability for people of all ages.

Types of mind maps.

According to Buzan (2006) cited in Hawrani (2011, p.17), there are many types of mind maps, these are:

1. Dyadic mind maps: those maps are made by drawing two radiant branches in the center.

2. Poly categoric mind maps: these maps can contain from three to seven branches

Because the average mind cannot remember more than seven pieces of information in the short term memory. One of the advantages of this type is that it helps develop the mental powers of classification and categorization.

3. Group mind maps: it is designed by bringing individuals together in mind mapping groups. According to Buzan (1994, p. 166), “ the mind map becomes the external reflection, “ the hard copy”, of the emerging group consensus and subsequently becomes a group record or memory. Through this process, the individual brains combine their energy to create a separate “ group brain”.

4. Computerized mind maps: these are designed by using computers. There are lots of mind mapping soft wares that help draw careful and cheerful mind maps such as, mind map which was designed by Tony Buzan, Free Mind, Mind Genius, Mind Jet, Nova Mind, and lots more.

There is a difference between hand-drawn mind maps and computerized mind maps or mind mapping software which should be mentioned. Table (2.1) shows the differences.

Table (2.1): hand drawn maps versus computerized mind maps/ mind mapping soft wares.

	Advantages	Disadvantages
Hand drawn maps	A. No Cost. B. No restrictions on map design and layout. C. May create map anytime with pencil and paper. D. Each map is a unique creation of the user. E. Collaboration is possible if colleagues are together in the same place	A. Cannot be digitally stored other than as a scanned document. B. Map size is limited. C. Preference of user for mind mapping software advantages.
Mind mapping software	A. Ability to link to other information such as hyperlinks and notes. B. Ability to modify and filter map Easily. C. Ability to integrate into other software. D. Ability to create templates easily. E. Ability to allow real collaboration. F. No size limits.	A. High cost of none free – source software. B. Requires computer access C. Learning curve of using software D. Map design flexibility restricted by software options E. Preference of user to hand-drawn map F. Map sharing restricted by format incompatibility

(Based on Tucker et al , 2008, p.4)

The mind mapping technique imitates the thinking process, namely possible for us to move from one topic to another topic back and forth. Recording the information through symbols, pictures, emotional meaning, and colors, exactly our brains process it. A pattern that at least consists of picture, symbol and color will not just help the students to understand the vocabulary knowledge but also makes the students feel good and enjoyable and attract their brain which at last lead them to have interest in mastering vocabulary knowledge. By implementing the mind mapping, students allow finding similar words, which has a relationship to the main word. They can work in groups or individually. They learn to share knowledge and information about targeted content and willingly do this because it is naturally following part of the class activity. By implementing the mind mapping technique in teaching, indirectly, students might be improved their knowledge of English vocabulary. At least it will be raised their self-confidence for expressing themselves openly, especially in English class. Students can share their knowledge and experience with others, including respectful listening and appropriate sharing of personal perspectives. Students also reported that their understanding of concepts was expressed and considered, at least we hope students can do not only in developing their vocabulary but also they are able to practice either in speaking or understanding of the meaning of words.

The Advantages of Using Mind Mapping Technique DePorter and Hernacki (in Abdurrahman, 2008: 172) describe that there are some advantages of using the mind mapping technique, they are as follows; 1. Flexible Explaining something can be easy without confusion in add the material based on the mind mapping. We can put the label and category of something based on our own opinion anywhere in the mind mapping. 2. Concentrate on the Topic Getting the subtopics that we talk about with a focus on the main ideas easily. Keeping the focus on the keyword can help us to make it simple and it does not waste the time. 3. Increasing Comprehension Using mind mapping can make it easy in understanding the material. Mind mapping is a simple thinking pattern so it does not make us confused to understand what we have learned and easy to remember the material. 4. Enjoyable Imagination and creativity are unlimited in using mind mapping, so it can be fun to learn. Using pictures and colors, it makes the brain enjoy and excited in thinking something that we want about the material. Parts of Mind Mapping Technique There are some parts of mind mapping (Windura, 2008: 77-86) namely; (1) central image, (2) keyword, (3) basic ordering ideas, (4) branches, (4) color and (5) picture. 1. Central Image A central image has to describe the main idea of a mind mapping and put it in the center of the paper. It is for making the learning activity enjoyable. 2. Key Word A keyword is a word that can lead a sentence or event. Identifying or another language that sounds like the new word and using only one keyword per line. It is an urge to remember a lot of words for the students. It is a strong noun or verb that creates an image to trigger the recall of the memory. 3. Basic Ordering Ideas. Basic ordering ideas are the branches that collect sort information and it connected to the central topic that radiates out from the center. Making basic ordering ideas which can direct our mind to make mind mapping and it needs creativity that encourages the students to understand to the material. It is thick and thinner at the ends. It can be seen as headings for your topic and spread anywhere but do not become steep. 4. Branches. The branches should be curvy and in the same length as the words or pictures above it. These branches can be seen as subheadings. It is thinner branches and contains details. 5. Colour . Colour is a very good memory sign and it involves the right brain in learning for long-term memory. Colors encourage creativity and help in memorization. Adding plenty of colours via branches, map background and images will add life to your mind map. It makes easier to comprehend and remember. 6. Picture In mind mapping, pictures that can change or strengthen a key.

4.1. Analysis of the Test The research began with a pre-test. The purpose of skills in English language words vocabulary. In pre-testing, the classroom teacher helped me to control the class. A pre-test is conducted on Monday, May 12 taken by 40 students, 20 boys, and 20 girls. Pretest consists of 120 words in English. In this test, the writer wanted to know how many words students know well. Student pre-test results were as follows: 27 students scored below 60, 4 students scored about 60, and 4 students scored more than 60. The average score on the pretest was 50. From the results of the pretest, the writer concluded that most students are not able to master English vocabulary well yet. The result of student achievement in the pre-test was 50%. The result is less than the desired criteria. Then, students gain vocabulary treatments by the mind mapping technique. Here students to know how to learn vocabulary using this technique. After completion of treatments and then at the end of the meeting students were given a post-test. The post-test was conducted on Monday, May 9, 2022. The test was used to know the students after getting the treatment of English mind mapping to teach English vocabulary. There were 120 words that were scored. There were no students who got scores less than 60. 7 students got scores about 60 and 33 students got scores more than 60. And the average of their scores was 82. From the analysis above, achievement in the post-test was higher than in the pretest. And the improvement of the achievement from the pre-test to the post-test was 64%.

5.1. Conclusion According to the findings and conclusion of the research, there are some conclusions can be drawn as follow: Mind mapping technique is one of the alternative technique in teaching vocabulary. The research result shows that this technique is vocabulary mastery. Moreover, mind mapping has been proven to have an effective influence in improving student vocabulary mastery. The experimental study shows that the improvement in vocabulary mastery of the experimental group is statistically than the improvement in the control group. The result of the questionnaires shows that most of the students agree that mind mapping is able to advance them, improve their vocabulary, expand their ideas, and increase their self-confidence in learning. Nevertheless, a good technique will not work well and help students if does not suit the student's needs and conditions. The mind mapping technique is still unable to recover vocabulary.

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